

A Prime-Generating Monic Cubic Polynomial with Run Length $L = 31$

Technical report for Zenodo deposition

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Abstract

We document a monic cubic integer polynomial $f(n)=n^3+54n^2-2329n+20507$ that generates 31 consecutive prime values for $n=0,1,\dots,30$ (primality tested on $|f(n)|$). The first composite value occurs at $n=31$, where $f(31)=29993=89\times 337$. This report summarizes the search domain used to discover the record, provides the Top 10 best triples (a,b,c) obtained in that run, and records the verification steps performed in Python and PARI/GP.

1. Polynomial and record definition

We consider monic cubic polynomials of the form:

$$f(n) = n^3 + a n^2 + b n + c$$

For a fixed triple (a,b,c) , define the run length L as the largest integer such that $|f(n)|$ is prime for all integers n with $0 \leq n \leq L-1$.

Record triple reported here:

$$a = 54, b = -2329, c = 20507$$

Claimed run length:

$$L = 31 \text{ (prime for } n = 0..30; \text{ first composite at } n = 31)$$

2. Search domain and data provenance

The discovery run that produced the Top 10 list in this report used the following domain:

$$a \in [-2500, +2500], b \in [-2500, +2500], c \in [2, 80000]$$

The attached CSV log (`cubic_L_ge20_searchi_2500.csv`) records each new record L found during the scan, including timestamp and coefficients.

3. Top 10 results from the run

Sorted by decreasing run length L (ties by earliest timestamp).

Rank	L	a	b	c	Timestamp (ISO)
1	31	54	-2329	20507	2025-12-14T14:59:58
2	30	23	-1988	24223	2025-12-14T14:49:08
3	30	57	-2218	18233	2025-12-14T15:01:02
4	29	-35	308	73	2025-12-14T14:28:40
5	29	14	-1239	16111	2025-12-14T14:46:06
6	29	26	-1939	22259	2025-12-14T14:50:10
7	29	60	-2101	16073	2025-12-14T15:02:07
8	28	-32	241	347	2025-12-14T14:29:44
9	28	17	-1208	14887	2025-12-14T14:47:07
10	28	29	-1884	20347	2025-12-14T14:51:13

4. Verification of the best triple $(a,b,c) = (54, -2329, 20507)$

4.1 Deterministic primality checks in Python

The polynomial values were computed for consecutive n starting at 0. For each value $v=f(n)$, primality was tested on $|v|$ with deterministic trial division up to $\text{floor}(\sqrt{|v|})$. The run stops at the first composite value.

Python check summary:

```
All |f(n)| are prime for n = 0..30; f(31) = 29993 is composite.
```

4.2 Independent verification in PARI/GP

The following PARI/GP snippet detects the first composite value:

```
for(n=0,200, if(!isprime(n^3+54*n^2-2329*n+20507), print("STOP a n=",n,"
valore=",n^3+54*n^2-2329*n+20507); break ) );
```

Observed PARI/GP output:

```
STOP a n=31 valore=29993
```

Factoring in PARI/GP confirms:

```
factor(29993) = 89 * 337
```

5. Prime values generated ($n = 0..30$)

Table of the 31 consecutive prime values produced by $f(n)=n^3+54n^2-2329n+20507$:

n	f(n)	prime?
0	20507	✓
1	18233	✓
2	16073	✓
3	14033	✓
4	12119	✓
5	10337	✓
6	8693	✓
7	7193	✓
8	5843	✓
9	4649	✓
10	3617	✓
11	2753	✓
12	2063	✓
13	1553	✓
14	1229	✓
15	1097	✓
16	1163	✓
17	1433	✓
18	1913	✓
19	2609	✓
20	3527	✓

n	f(n)	prime?
21	4673	✓
22	6053	✓
23	7673	✓
24	9539	✓
25	11657	✓
26	14033	✓
27	16673	✓
28	19583	✓
29	22769	✓
30	26237	✓

First composite value

At $n = 31$:

$$f(31) = 29993 = 89 \times 337 \text{ (composite)}$$

6. Notes on reproducibility

The record can be reproduced by evaluating the polynomial for consecutive integers n starting at 0 and applying a deterministic primality test to $|f(n)|$, stopping at the first composite value.

Recommended independent checks include: (i) a separate implementation of primality testing (e.g., trial division, deterministic Miller-Rabin for 32-bit/64-bit ranges) and (ii) a CAS/tool such as PARI/GP using `isprime()` and `factor()`.